

Isolation and Characterization of the Unexpected 1-*n*-Octyloxyperopyrene: a Solution-processable p-Type Organic Semiconductor

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-Supporting Information-

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1. NMR spectra

Figure S1: ^1H NMR Spectrum of compound 1 (500 MHz, $1,1,2,2$ -Tetrachloroethane- d_2 , 298 K).

Figure S2: ^{13}C NMR Spectrum of compound 1 (125 MHz, $1,1,2,2$ -Tetrachloroethane- d_2 , 363 K).

2. X-ray Crystallographic Studies

Crystals grew as clear, orange needles (0.242 x 0.062 x 0.025 mm³) by slow evaporation from chloroform. The experiments were performed by Dr. Leire San Felices, from the X-ray diffraction unit of General Services SG-Iker (UPV/EHU). Intensity data were collected on an Agilent Technologies Super-Nova diffractometer, which was equipped with monochromated Cu α radiation ($\lambda = 1.54184 \text{ \AA}$) and Atlas CCD detector. Measurement was carried out at 150.00(10) K with the help of an Oxford Cryostream 700 PLUS temperature device. Data frames were processed (unit cell determination, analytical absorption correction with face indexing, intensity data integration and correction for Lorentz and polarization effects) using the CrysAlis software package. The structure was solved using Olex2 and refined by full-matrix least-squares with SHELXL-97. Final geometrical calculations were carried out with Mercury and PLATON as integrated in WinGX.

The crystallographic data for the structure reported in this paper have been deposited with the Cambridge Crystallographic Data Centre as supplementary publication (CCDC number 1862521).

Figure S3: ORTEP projection of the X-ray structure **1** with 50% probability atomic displacement ellipsoids is displayed.

Figure S4: ORTEP diagram of the two independent molecules present in the asymmetric unit of compound **1**, showing 50% probability ellipsoids.

Table S1. Crystal data and structure refinement for compound **1**.

Empirical formula	C ₃₄ H ₃₀ O
Formula weight	454.58
Crystal system	Monoclinic
Space group	P2 ₁ /n
a (Å)	8.2223(5)
b (Å)	13.7606(7)
c (Å)	41.901(3)
α (°)	90.0
β (°)	92.920(6)
γ (°)	90.0
V (Å³)	4734.7(5)
Z	8
d (calculated) (g/cm³)	1.275
μ (mm⁻¹)	0.572
F (000)	1936.0
h	-9 ≤ h ≤ 6
k	-16 ≤ k ≤ 16
l	-50 ≤ l ≤ 51
collected reflections	38166
independent reflections	8951
R_{int}	0.0714
GOF in F²	1.166
R₁ [I > 2σ(I)]	0.1194
wR(F²) [I > 2σ(I)]	0.3253
R₁ (all data)	0.1608
wR(F²) (all data)	0.3710

3. Theoretical calculations

Figure S5: Csp²-Csp² bonds alternation for compound **1** from a) solid state and b) B3LYP-6-31G(d,p) in vacuum coloured by a scheme that highlights the bond alternation. Bonds are rendered in a colour continuum ranging from red (1.34 Å) to white (1.40 Å) to blue (1.46 Å) so that Clar's aromatic sextets are lighter/white colours.

Figure S6: Optimized structures (unfunctionalized peropyrene, **1**-Extended conformation and **1**-Folded conformation) with their computed total energies.

Figure S7: B3LYP-6-31G(d,p) level HOMO and LUMO for compound **1** from side (top) and top (bottom) view.

Table S2. Frontier orbitals computed with the B3LYP with the 6-31G(d,p) and 6-311+G(2d,p) basis set in dichloromethane and chloroform on B3LYP-6-31G(d,p) geometries for the molecule **1** and unfunctionalized peropyrene. All values in eV.

B3LYP-6-31G(d,p)		LUMO+2	LUMO+1	LUMO	HOMO	HOMO-1	HOMO-2	gap
Unfunctionalized peropyrene	vacuum	-0.57	-0.96	-2.04	-4.85	-6.03	-6.33	2.81
1 -Extended conformation	vacuum	-0.4	-0.85	-1.86	-4.6	-5.9	-6.02	2.74
1 -Folded conformation	vacuum	-0.44	-0.9	-1.9	-4.63	-5.92	-6.05	2.73
B3LYP-CH ₂ CL ₂ -6-311+G(2d,p)/B3LYP-6-31G(d,p)								
1 -Extended conformation	dichloromethane	-0.91	-1.32	-2.23	-4.95	-6.22	-6.36	2.72
1 -Folded conformation	dichloromethane	-0.9	-1.31	-2.22	-4.93	-6.19	-6.35	2.71
B3LYP-CHCL ₃ -6-311+G(2d,p)/B3LYP-6-31G(d,p)								
1 -Extended conformation	chloroform	-0.89	-1.29	-2.2	-4.92	-6.2	-6.33	2.72
1 -Folded conformation	chloroform	-0.89	-1.29	-2.2	-4.92	-6.2	-6.33	2.72

DFT Cartesian coordinates: Unfunctionalized peropyrene

40

```
pp_cs.log      Energy: -627078.4207766
C      4.98605    1.20711    0.00003
C      3.58132    1.22939    0.00003
C      2.85543    0.00009    0.00000
C      3.58123   -1.22921   -0.00002
C      4.98593   -1.20688   -0.00003
C      5.68023    0.00016    0.00000
C      1.42075    0.00013   -0.00001
C      0.71273   -1.24302   -0.00003
C      1.47964   -2.45738   -0.00003
C      2.84079   -2.45426   -0.00004
C      0.71271    1.24298   -0.00001
C     -0.71303    1.24314   -0.00004
C     -1.42060   -0.00015   -0.00002
C     -0.71249   -1.24301   -0.00001
C      2.84067    2.45419    0.00007
C      1.47942    2.45719    0.00006
C     -1.47966    2.45729   -0.00006
C     -2.84111    2.45418   -0.00006
C     -3.58117    1.22918   -0.00003
C     -2.85538   -0.00013   -0.00001
C     -4.98615    1.20710   -0.00001
C     -5.68023    0.00010    0.00002
C     -4.98582   -1.20699    0.00004
C     -3.58127   -1.22946    0.00003
C     -2.84054   -2.45437    0.00005
C     -1.47943   -2.45742    0.00004
H      5.52702    2.14954    0.00005
H      6.76621   -0.00020   -0.00000
H      0.96699   -3.41109   -0.00004
H      3.38931   -3.39240   -0.00005
H      3.38888    3.39253    0.00012
H      0.96699    3.41104    0.00011
H     -0.96749    3.41126   -0.00009
H     -3.38914    3.39253   -0.00008
H     -5.52702    2.14951   -0.00003
H     -6.76621   -0.00039    0.00003
H     -5.52693   -2.14939    0.00006
H     -3.38912   -3.39249    0.00008
H     -0.96671   -3.41109    0.00007
H      5.52712   -2.14918   -0.00005
```

DFT Cartesian coordinates: 1-Extended conformation

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1mol_uc_Cs.log Energy: -871647.7194693

O	2.05466	1.92281	0.00000
C	0.69423	2.01040	0.00000
C	-0.00957	3.21748	0.00000
H	0.51669	4.16386	0.00000
C	-1.40213	3.20976	0.00000
H	-1.93988	4.15400	0.00000
C	-2.13002	2.01294	0.00000
C	-3.55955	1.98752	0.00000
H	-4.09567	2.93301	0.00000
C	-4.24572	0.81220	0.00000
H	-5.32774	0.84617	0.00000
C	-3.57703	-0.45917	0.00000
C	-4.29178	-1.69203	0.00000
C	-5.72687	-1.74552	0.00000
H	-6.29442	-0.82334	0.00000
C	-6.40852	-2.92380	0.00000
H	-7.49524	-2.92613	0.00000
C	-5.72157	-4.17979	0.00000
C	-6.40794	-5.40547	0.00000
H	-7.49458	-5.39997	0.00000
C	-5.71257	-6.61218	0.00000
H	-6.25835	-7.55118	0.00000
C	-4.32052	-6.61883	0.00000
H	-3.77760	-7.56013	0.00000
C	-3.59499	-5.41507	0.00000
C	-2.16424	-5.38996	0.00000
H	-1.62756	-6.33491	0.00000
C	-1.47842	-4.21350	0.00000
H	-0.39615	-4.24848	0.00000
C	-2.14363	-2.94182	0.00000
C	-1.42689	-1.70778	0.00000
C	0.00579	-1.65468	0.00000
H	0.57386	-2.57651	0.00000
C	0.69066	-0.47647	0.00000
H	1.77402	-0.47021	0.00000
C	0.00000	0.77364	0.00000
C	-1.42378	0.77120	0.00000
C	-2.14528	-0.47101	0.00000
C	-3.57281	-2.92923	0.00000
C	-4.29382	-4.17004	0.00000
C	2.82912	3.12208	0.00000
H	2.58710	3.72291	0.88843
H	2.58710	3.72291	-0.88843
C	4.30012	2.73147	0.00000
H	4.49873	2.10790	-0.88011
H	4.49873	2.10790	0.88011
C	5.22513	3.95495	0.00000

H	5.00658	4.57894	0.87810
H	5.00658	4.57894	-0.87810
C	6.71483	3.58967	0.00000
H	6.93557	2.96646	0.87784
H	6.93557	2.96646	-0.87784
C	7.63887	4.81356	0.00000
H	7.41449	5.43643	-0.87769
H	7.41449	5.43643	0.87769
C	9.13061	4.45845	0.00000
H	9.35685	3.83617	-0.87771
H	9.35685	3.83617	0.87771
C	10.05141	5.68510	0.00000
H	9.82473	6.30631	-0.87715
H	9.82473	6.30631	0.87715
C	11.53997	5.32495	0.00000
H	11.80470	4.73314	-0.88361
H	11.80470	4.73314	0.88361
H	12.16929	6.22083	0.00000

DFT Cartesian coordinates: 1-Folded conformation

65

1mol_uc.xyz.siman.opt.log Energy: -871643.6599913

O	4.05653	0.19845	-1.70103
C	3.17813	1.03794	-1.08062
C	3.52121	2.27176	-0.51931
H	4.54414	2.62603	-0.53934
C	2.54231	3.06067	0.07919
H	2.82184	4.01813	0.51029
C	1.20492	2.64914	0.14725
C	0.19030	3.44430	0.76532
H	0.47077	4.40382	1.19189
C	-1.10149	3.01986	0.82550
H	-1.83270	3.65820	1.30485
C	-1.51403	1.75840	0.27619
C	-2.86451	1.30742	0.34190
C	-3.90252	2.08442	0.95932
H	-3.66188	3.04840	1.38969
C	-5.19124	1.65085	1.02493
H	-5.95067	2.26587	1.50031
C	-5.57903	0.38668	0.47653
C	-6.90345	-0.07797	0.53646
H	-7.65743	0.54196	1.01399
C	-7.25110	-1.31289	-0.00549
H	-8.27953	-1.65765	0.04945
C	-6.28492	-2.10670	-0.61720
H	-6.55572	-3.07044	-1.03986
C	-4.94851	-1.67931	-0.69901
C	-3.93362	-2.47333	-1.32130
H	-4.21164	-3.43623	-1.74135
C	-2.64365	-2.04273	-1.39088
H	-1.91281	-2.68184	-1.87044
C	-2.23014	-0.77979	-0.84898
C	-0.87875	-0.32700	-0.91956
C	0.15467	-1.09746	-1.54678
H	-0.08922	-2.05253	-1.99467
C	1.44711	-0.66874	-1.60868
H	2.20142	-1.27189	-2.09903
C	1.83459	0.58287	-1.03878
C	0.83898	1.38902	-0.41654
C	-0.52385	0.93775	-0.35350
C	-3.21754	0.03916	-0.21887
C	-4.57672	-0.41598	-0.14753
C	5.45044	0.52518	-1.76950
H	5.56882	1.57726	-2.05619
H	5.82701	-0.08258	-2.59844
C	6.23189	0.21206	-0.49019
H	5.74423	0.69419	0.36393
H	7.21051	0.70017	-0.59429
C	6.46655	-1.28338	-0.20839

H	7.18143	-1.36157	0.62191
H	6.97086	-1.72317	-1.08018
C	5.22736	-2.13134	0.12810
H	4.51285	-2.08845	-0.70165
H	5.54678	-3.17979	0.20534
C	4.51526	-1.73751	1.42951
H	5.23340	-1.77527	2.26250
H	4.17469	-0.69763	1.36392
C	3.31934	-2.64483	1.75126
H	3.66004	-3.68962	1.75849
H	2.58294	-2.56891	0.93893
C	2.62575	-2.34226	3.08951
H	1.87341	-3.11948	3.27554
H	3.35861	-2.43080	3.90382
C	1.94785	-0.96892	3.15915
H	2.66981	-0.15081	3.07070
H	1.42122	-0.83868	4.11038
H	1.21483	-0.84836	2.35377

4. Thermal behavior

Figure S8: TGA of compound **1**.

Figure S9: POM texture of compound **1** at 160 °C under crossed polarizers, appearing from the isotropic liquid.

5. Powder X-ray diffraction

Figure S10: X-Ray powder diffraction pattern at room temperature for compound **1**: as-obtained powder (top), obtained from chloroform evaporation, and after annealing at 150°C (bottom).

6. Devices

Table S3. Electrical characterization for compound **1** deposited on substrate by spin-coated thin film. Values of mobility, threshold voltage (V_{tr}) and on/off ratio current ($I_{on/off}$) are reported.

W (μm)	L (μm)	Mobility (cm^2/Vs)	V_{tr}	I_{on}/I_{off}	Mobility (cm^2/Vs)	V_t	I_{on}/I_{off}
		r.t.			Annealing 150°C		
10000	2.5	1.50E-04	-10.5	27.0			
		7.80E-05			1.61E-03	22.0	33.0
		1.56E-04	-10	27.0	7.77E-04	4.0	24.1
		6.78E-05	-5	22.4	7.19E-04	15.5	24.1
10000	5	8.43E-05	-16.5	13.6	2.77E-04	22.0	13.8
		1.17E-04	-14	17.5	1.22E-04	17.0	9.5
		1.17E-04	-10	18.5	4.53E-04	11.5	15.5
		1.12E-04	-9.5	18.9	6.59E-04	14.5	19.0
10000	10	8.67E-05	-10.5	12.1	7.92E-05	16.0	5.7
		9.36E-05	-15.5	11.6	1.06E-04	17.0	6.5
		8.44E-05	-12	11.9	3.28E-05	9.0	3.7
		1.03E-04	-11	12.4	6.36E-05	8.5	4.8
10000	20	8.68E-05	-12.5	8.58	3.34E-06	12.0	1.6
		5.94E-05	-17	6.73	2.27E-06	19.0	1.6
		9.34E-05	-13.5	8.4	1.56E-05	19.5	2.5
		7.17E-05	-13	8.1	1.73E-06	18.5	1.5
Average:		9.76E-05	-12	14.978	3.28E-04	14.1	10.4
Standard deviation		2.73E-05			4.51E-04		